

DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL STABILITY OF CLUSTERS IN AGRICULTURE

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Annotation: This article discusses the role of the credit system in financial support of agricultural producers and the development of state and market mechanisms for regulating the credit system.

Keywords: banking and financial system, economic and financial sector, commercial banks, system of supporting institutions, credit system, economic growth, modernization, innovative development, self-regulating market mechanism.

In recent years, our country has been undergoing progressive changes in every field, enriched with modern technical technologies, in particular, the changes in agriculture, which are being carried out on the initiative of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, are no exception. In particular, in each of our regions, significant changes are taking place in the agricultural system, for example, if we take cotton cultivation, which is the national wealth of our country, as an example, previously we exported cotton fiber to foreign countries, which we could only use as raw materials. Today, with the initiatives of our head of state, the area of cotton fields is being reduced, and instead of these, projects are being implemented to produce agricultural products, namely, to form intensive gardens, expand vegetable cultivation, and to export the fruits of our paradise, melon crops, to saturate our domestic market with our finished products. The integration process taking place in the world economy is having a great impact on its globalization. On the one hand, this provides for a transnational "chain" of added value creation, and on the other hand, it also increases competition in the production sector. On the basis of globalization, a global communication system is also developing, which ensures the standardization of logistics and the quality of goods and services. In addition, the

constant increase in the population requires the creation of employment and a convenient work process for the population. A small level of integration is considered a way to form a new economic system in the economies of countries, which consists in the creation of "Clusters" that include enterprises and organizations that produce mutually related products and are geographically close.

The agricultural sector in a market economy must independently ensure the functioning of special institutions for supporting agricultural producers and the rural population. Each country creates its own system of supporting institutions, the main features of which are explained by the high level of state participation, especially in the initial stages of their formation.

The development of the agrarian sector of the economy largely depends on the stability of the financial and economic situation of agricultural producers. However, the lack of internal and external sources of financing not only for expanded, but also for simple reproduction in most agricultural entities increases the need and role of state regulation of the agricultural credit system.

State regulation of the agricultural credit system is a complex process aimed at creating conditions for the practical implementation of its important functions and includes: - ensuring the stability of the system;

- borrowers' solvency;

- stimulation of agricultural development.

The sustainable development of the credit system is closely related to the state's participation in the creation of the necessary production capacities (profitability of agricultural production, availability of means of production, availability of a system for the sale, transportation and storage of agricultural products, availability of solvent demand in the market) and financial (access to credit institutions, availability of information for risk assessment, freedom to make

decisions on lending, quality and sufficient amount of credit capital, effective methods for assessing the borrower's creditworthiness, mechanism for ensuring the fulfillment of obligations) conditions have been created for the functioning of effective forms of credit support for agricultural producers.

State regulation of the credit system in agriculture makes it possible to influence the dynamics of its development. In this regard, the indicator of the coverage of potential borrowers of agriculture serves as a guide in choosing forms and methods of state influence, the effectiveness of which is characterized by the creation of conditions that ensure a multiple increase in the number of credit transactions, ensuring a multiplicative growth in the number of credit transactions and an increase in their value for both parties to the individual. If the credit system moves towards expanding credit transactions, increasing the coverage of agricultural producers, state regulation will be effective, otherwise transactions will be relatively reduced, the credit system will close and face decline.

In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the use of the cluster method in creating a perfect innovative image of the country and society. A vivid example of this is the efforts in the agricultural sector. It is noteworthy that the number of cotton-textile clusters is currently increasing, in the future 70 out of 133 cotton-growing districts will transition to a full cluster system, and it is planned to establish 41 enterprises and create about 25 thousand jobs by newly formed clusters. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the development of agroclusters is the most correct way. Because even in years that are unfavorable for agriculture, the total number of jobs and wages is maintained at the expense of other organizations of the cluster. That is, the impact of the vagaries of nature on business and workers' incomes is reduced. The possibility of crop rotation appears and soil fertility is restored. Our foreign enterprise "VST Cluster", established on the basis of the resolution of the President of Uzbekistan on measures to establish a modern cotton-textile cluster in the Bukhara region of May 19, 2017, is also operating according to such criteria. A total of eight companies will be established in this cluster system. Uzbekistan made the

right choice in choosing a cluster system in the cotton-textile sector. For example, Turkey has managed to gain a strong position in the world textile market in 20-25 years. I think that your country, thanks to the cluster, will achieve such a result in the next two to three years. The reason for this is the rapid changes taking place in your country, especially the attention paid to the development of the cluster sector based on the specific characteristics of each region. The head of our state has repeatedly emphasized that the path to becoming one of the most advanced countries in the world is the introduction of cluster systems in the agricultural sector, science, education and other areas. These include light industry, oil and gas, chemistry, biotechnology, ICT, automotive, transport and logistics, recreation and tourism, food, education, fisheries, poultry farming, beekeeping, sericulture. The creation of cluster systems in these areas will increase the volume and improve the quality of financing for scientific research and development. It will create new opportunities for participation in external investment projects, training and improving the skills of scientific and pedagogical personnel. In our country, many state programs that are extremely important for the development of agriculture have always been underfunded. These programs include agricultural research, knowledge dissemination, agricultural education, soil fertility improvement, food security system development, veterinary and phytosanitary services, business support (agricultural cooperatives, clusters, effective partnerships), statistical and market data collection and analysis, market infrastructure and agrolistics development, environmental protection, policy analysis, staff training at any level, and monitoring. In the future, these programs may require significant amounts of government funding.

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